

SELF-EFFICACY, PERCEIVED SOCIAL SUPPORT, AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF WORKING STUDENTS

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Self-Efficacy, Perceived Social Support, and Academic Performance of Working Students

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Abstract

The study's aim is to explore how self-efficacy, perceived social support and academic performance are related to one another when it comes to working students. The study used purposive sampling which included 61 female and 41 male working students in National University Fairview with ages 18-30 years old. The study utilized correlational research design. It was found that 68.60% were part-time employees with an average grade of 3.02. Test of normality was used to assess the normality of the distribution, using Kolmogorov-Smirnov. The results of the study show that self-efficacy has a significant relationship with academic performance and with perceived social support of the selected NU Fairview working students. However, there is no significant relationship between academic performance and perceived social support. By being ready for such situations, they can really be prepared to face them when they arise. When a working student is aware of his or her limitations in terms of academic performance, they may manage and handle situations appropriately. The levels and correlations between working students' academic achievement, perceived social support, and self-efficacy have been determined by the researchers using a correlational design. The presence of a linear relationship between quantitative variables was ascertained using Pearson's correlation.

Keywords: *students, breadwinners, work, school, parents*

Introduction

The research aims to address how students' perceived social support in the environment and their academic performances are influenced by their level of self-efficacy. The start of college life can be a stressful event for students. The close social relationships that students can encounter, and their own self-efficacy can have positive consequences on their well-being. The scope of the student is the currently working students of National University Fairview with the age range of 18 to 30 years old. The participants will be selected purposely. The standardized questionnaire focused on how self-efficacy and perceived social support affects their academic performance as a working student. Many students need to work to meet their financial responsibilities due to the rising cost of tuition. Attaining a college degree does not always increase the wage gap either, but other academic and personal characteristics have approximately the same influence on the wages of college graduates. The research found that being a working student may cause positive and negative effects on their studies or life. Positively, it shows that it may help young adults; it helps them to stand on their own and be independent, and they may also gain long-lasting friendships with their co-workers and other students who work with them. Abenoja (2019) stated that students who are working part-time tend to achieve poorer marks compared to their classmates who are studying full-time.

Many parents and guardians can no longer support or shoulder the full financial responsibility to send their children to college. In addition, the limited number of scholarships is highly competitive and student loans are insufficient to pay for everything. Given this reality, there is a rise in the number of students who work while in college. Creed et al. (2015) stated that work-based benefits (enabling resources, rewards, and involvement); higher work- university conflict was associated with more time demands and fewer psychological rewards; facilitation was associated with greater engagement (dedication), general well- being, and conflict was associated with greater negative feelings toward the university. Working while studying is related to students' engagement and well-being. It is essential to the growth of human capital and is associated with a person's wellbeing and prospects for a better quality of life. Over the past ten years, there has been a tremendous rise in the employment rate of college students. With an increase in the number of students taking part-time jobs outside campus, its effect on students' academic performance has been questioned by many researchers. The researchers sought to understand how other students could balance their employment and academic success. The study aims to discuss the relationship of self-efficacy, perceived social support, and students' academic performance as measured by their general weighted average (GWA). The scope of the student is the currently working students at National University Fairview Campus with the age range of 18 to 30 years old. Standardized questionnaires focused on self-efficacy and perceived social support were used to relate to the academic performance of the participants.

Methodology

The researchers used a correlational design to get information about the levels and relationships of the self-efficacy, perceived social support, and academic performance of working students. Pearson's correlation was used to determine the existence of a linear relationship between quantitative variables.

Purposive Sampling was used in selecting the participants which included 61 female and 41 male working students in National University Fairview, aged 18-30 years old as per the participants. Test of normality was used to assess the normality of the distribution, using Kolmogorov-Smirnov. The study utilized a quantitative research design through survey questionnaires, specifically correlational, through the use of standardized questionnaires. All of these participants are selected purposely. This sampling method is conducted where each member of the university has the qualification of being a working student to become part of a sample. The chosen

participants are from different college levels. Each of the participants answered a standardized questionnaire. The purpose of standardized questionnaires is to gather information on how self-efficacy and perceived social support affects their academic performance as a working student that will be needed in this study.

The General Self-Efficacy (GSE) Questionnaire by Ralf Schwarzer and Matthias Jerusalem was used to measure self-efficacy. It is a Likert scale test with 10 items. A mean score of 10 to 19.9 reflects low self-efficacy, 20 to 29.9 reflects moderate levels, while 30 to 40 reflects high self-efficacy.

Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social by Gregory Zimet was used to measure perceived social support. This consists of 12 items using a 5-point Likert scale (0 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). To interpret this questionnaire, a mean score between 1 and 2.9 is interpreted as low social support, 3 to 5 could be is in interpreted as moderate social support, and 5.1 to 7 is seen as high support.

Results and Discussion

What is the level of academic performance (as measured by general weighted average) of the working students?

Table 1. *Mean and SD of Academic Performance using General Weighted Average*

	Mean	SD
Academic Performance	3.02	0.49

Table 1 shows that the mean score of academic performance using the general weighted average is 3.02 which is interpreted as good to above average grade from the institution. This data shows that being a working student does not hinder achieving good academic performance. Research also shows that academically good students have better employment benefits, higher income, higher self-esteem, and are less likely to engage in substance abuse (Tadese, et.al, 2022).

What is the level of self-efficacy of the selected working students?

Table 2. *Mean and SD of Self-Efficacy*

	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Academic Performance	30.27	4.80	High

Table 2 shows that the mean score of self-efficacy is 30.27 which falls under high level since it is between 30 to 40. According to this method, any mean scale score between 30 and 40 could be considered high support, 20.1 to 29.99 could be considered moderate support, and 1 to 19.99 could be considered low support.

What is the level of perceived social support of the selected working students?

Table 3. *Mean and SD of Perceived Social Support*

	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Perceived Social Support	5.08	1.31	High

It can be observed that the mean score of perceived social support is 5.08 which falls under high level since the mean score is between 5.01 to 7. According to this method, any mean scale score between 1 and 2.9 could be considered low support, 3 to 5 could be considered moderate support, and 5.1 to 7 could be considered high support.

Is there a significant relationship of self-efficacy to academic performance, and perceived social support of the selected working students?

Table 4. *Pearson Correlation Analysis of Self-Efficacy to Academic Performance, and Perceived Social Support*

Self-Efficacy	Pearson-R	p-value	Interpretation
Academic Performance	0.20	0.04	Significant Correlation
Perceived Social Support	0.32	0.00	Significant Correlation

Pearson correlation shows a relationship of 0.20 which shows a significant relationship between academic performance and self-efficacy of the selected NU Fairview working students. While the Pearson correlation shows a relationship of 0.32 which shows a significant relationship between perceived social support and self-efficacy of the selected NU Fairview working students. The data analysis shows that p-value is less than 0.05 which means that there is significant correlation between the variables.

Is there a significant relationship between perceived social support and academic performance of the selected working students?

Table 5. *Pearson Correlation Analysis Between Perceived Social Support and Academic Performance*

<i>Perceived Social Support</i>	<i>Pearson-R</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Academic Performance	-0.04	0.96	No Significant Correlation

The data analysis shows that p-value is greater than 0.05 where $p = 0.96$ at 95% level of confidence. Pearson correlation shows a relationship of -0.04 which shows no relationship between academic performance and perceived social support of the selected NU Fairview working students.

Conclusions

The purpose of this research was to identify if there is a relationship between self-efficacy, perceived social support, and academic performance of NU Fairview working students. Based on the analysis conducted, there is no relationship between perceived social support and academic performance of NU Fairview working students. According to Husaini (2023), the most important elements impacting a students' academic performance may be negatively impacted if they do not have the support of their peers or perhaps receive insufficient assistance from them. Studies also show that working students who have adequate social support can succeed academically as well as professionally. Additionally, other students believe that family support is not a benefit but rather a burden, especially for those who are working students. This research shows that the relationship between academic performance and self-efficacy has been observed among NU Fairview working students. If a working student has well-built beliefs from his or her experiences or what has been taught, then having strong academic achievement is possible. Every working student needs to be aware of this in order to succeed academically and avoid getting easily frustrated when little things go wrong. According to Doménech-Betoret (2017), it is important to know their strengths and weaknesses in terms of their capabilities to handle future situations, being prepared for some situations that might encounter, they can know how to handle that situation when it comes. In relation to academic performance of a working student, when the working student knows his or her capabilities, they can manage and handle things accordingly. Also, the relationship between perceived social support and self-efficacy has been observed as well among NU Fairview working students. Some studies have clearly defined that perceived social support goes high, somehow self-efficacy also goes high which can also be observed among NU Fairview working students based on the analysis concluded.

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